

IMPROVEMENT OF THE METHOD OF DRAWING THE TARE OF NEWLY BUILT CARGO WAGONS OF "QUYUV – MEXANIKA ZAVODI" SHK

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Anotation: Uniformity in terms of metrology and standardization and certification requirements has been agreed on the basis of Jaxon standards. But based on the laws of gravity and following the principles of universal gravitation, it is possible to understand that objects are heaviest at the poles of our planet and lightest at the equator. A brief analysis of this situation was made.

Key words: Cast mechanics, gravity principle, wagon, weight, scale, train, earth planet, ton, km, tare.

As we can see, "Uzbekistan Railways" JSC, which is making a great contribution to the economy of our country, is achieving great changes and successes. In particular, freight turnover in the country is 23.6 billion ton-km, 1795 million pass-km. Railway lines with a total length of more than 7400 km are being used safely.

It is the duty of every railway employee to ensure safe movement of trains, safe delivery of passengers and goods to their destination and their integrity. Today, it is the task of us railway workers to prevent and eliminate defects and deficiencies that pose a threat to the movement.

To date, 6 different types of freight wagons are being produced and exported to foreign countries at "Quyuv – mexanika zavodi" ShK. The technical parameters of the produced freight wagons are being monitored. We will consider below the control of the net weight (tare) of the wagon from these technical indicators.

Our planet Earth is not spherical. It is aligned at the poles and extends along the equator. The radius of the Earth at the equator is 21 kilometers longer than the

radius of the poles. This means that gravity at the equator acts a little farther. That is why the weight of the same body is different in different parts of our planet. Following the principles of universal gravitation, it can be understood that objects are heaviest at the poles of our planet and lightest at the equator. Compared to the weight at the poles, objects at the equator are 1/190 lighter. Such a change in weight can only be determined on a spring balance. In addition, centrifugal forces appear as a result of the rotation of the planet at the equator, so the weight of objects additionally decreases a little. As a result, the weight of an adult person coming from the center of the Arctic Circle to the equator decreases by about 0.5 kilograms.

Accounting for goods transported by rail is of great importance for the organization of traffic and the correct operation of rolling stock, as well as for commercial calculations. In order to ensure a high-quality technological process on the entrance roads of industrial enterprises and intra-plant transportation (for example, when loading blast furnaces and marten furnaces), it is equally important to take into account the loads transported on the wagon scales. Towing the vehicle is equally important.

The first devices for weighing in motion were mainly static wagon scales, and the train moved very slowly to reduce the dynamic component. A special signaling system has been developed to help the driver maintain a speed of 3 km per hour. Nevertheless, the error remained high (more than 1%), and the weighing process was complex and lengthy.

The net weight of freight wagons manufactured at "Quyuv – mexanika zavodi" ShK is measured and controlled using a BBC-150-2-BF static scale. This process takes a lot of time, that is, maneuvering is required to weigh each wagon separately.

Currently, TENZO-10 scales are popular, and these scales are able to measure the weight of wagons while moving at a speed of 5 km/h.

In conclusion: From the above, it can be seen that, if TENZO-10 scales are

used instead of BBC-150-2-BF static scales, the performance will increase significantly.

References

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